

PROSPECTIVE DIRECTIONS OF INTRODUCING INNOVATIVE DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TOURISM

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Abstract. This article examines the formation of tourism infrastructure, the use of innovative digital technologies, the acceleration of the use of innovative technologies in modern and brand hotels and affordable accommodation facilities such as hostels and family guest houses, as well as the implementation of mechanisms for providing apartments according to the AirB&B system.

Keywords: tourism, innovation, perspective, hotel, digital economy, tour package.

INTRODUCTION. As a result of the reforms implemented in our republic in recent years, there are issues that require special attention. Similarly, in 1995, the American programmer Nicholas Negroponte coined the term "digital economy". Currently, this term is used by politicians, economists, journalists, businessmen - almost everyone around the world.

The decision of the President "On measures to develop the digital economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan"[1] and the Cabinet of Ministers' decision on August 31, 2018, which defines the goals and objectives of the digital economy, "Addition on the introduction and further development of the digital economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan made a decision on measures"2]. Based on this, our tasks in front of us are to develop tourism and service development and develop development directions, to study what the main attention is focused on when introducing innovative technologies to the tourism infrastructure.

The level of study of the problem. The formation and implementation of the digital economy in the service sector is a complex process that depends on many factors. Leading foreign scientists Don Topscott, Alex Topscott [3] Paul Vigna, Michael Casey have different views on the application of digital innovative technologies in the economy, developing the theoretical aspects of these processes and putting them into practice. Including, in the field of tourism, Carmen Babaita, Gabriela Sipos, Andreia Ispas, and Andrea Nagular, in their textbook "Leadership style and culture for innovation in hotel industry", discuss the role of innovative technologies in the development of tourism infrastructure [4]. Another foreign scholar, Artura Kunllas, published a work called "Innovation in hospitality management" in which he conducted research on achieving efficiency by applying innovative management methods in hotels [5]. The authors may not have paid enough attention to the processes of applying innovative technologies in the implementation of the considered factors. Among the scientists of our country S. Ghulomov[6] made a great contribution to the application and introduction of digital and information technologies, innovations in the economy.

Research methodology. In the research, the methodology of taking into account the innovative changes expected in the coming years in determining the development of the digital economy in the development of tourism and thereby studying the development of tourism as a whole infrastructure is used. a method of defining the directions of development of tourism infrastructure components is proposed.

Analysis and results. Digital economy is not a separate type of activity. Basically, it means entrepreneurship, business, industrial facilities, services. The term "digital" refers to the active use of innovative information technologies in all these areas. If in the traditional economy, the basis of material goods is considered a resource, in the digital economy it will be information and data that can be processed and transmitted. After their analysis, a proper management solution is developed.

In Uzbekistan, the term "digital economy" has been used in our national legislation for recent years. Work in this regard started 10-15 years ago in all developed countries, and they have already begun to form it. We must not be left out of the process. Because we are among the countries that are rapidly entering globalization and integration with the world community.

To conclude from the above, the digital economy is a hybrid economy. This can be possible due to the development of information and communication and financial technologies, as well as the openness of the infrastructure, which provides the opportunity for full interaction of all subjects of economic activity in hybrid tourism and service provision - objects of the creation, distribution, exchange, consumption process of goods and services.

For example, a tourist wants to go on a trip to the country he previously planned to visit and visits the tour operator's office. He sits face-to-face with him, familiarizes himself with the tour packages, and buys the tour package he likes for cash, this is a traditional economy. Choosing a suitable tour package through the Internet address of tour operators, paying money to the account of the tour operator through an electronic payment system and receiving the tour package and tour services is called digital economy. This is the simplest example to explain.

Based on this, in our opinion, the digital economy in service delivery is not a new process that needs to be developed or introduced, it means changing the existing services in a new way by introducing innovative technologies in the daily life of tourists.² An example of this is the current changes in the world tourism industry. Turning to the changes in the hotel business, social and technological changes were observed in the hotel business in 2017-2019 as a result of the introduction of innovations, and there are great opportunities for hotels with large and famous brands to take the initiative in this regard. This determines the main directions of innovations that are expected to be used in the world hotel business. These directions include the following.

1. New types of fees and charges will be introduced in the hotel business. As a result, according to international experts, the price of hotel rooms in the US tourism market will increase in the future. According to experts, there is also a positive side to this, as opposed to increasing the price of the rooms, it is envisaged that the city taxes will not be charged for staying in the hotels with the introduced fees.

2. Innovative technologies used in rooms. According to Edmundson, manager of a chain of the famous "Marriott" hotel chain, in the near future in the hotel business, "internet items" - investments focused on connecting devices such as "Nest" smart thermostat or voice assistant "Alexa" will attract everyone's attention.

For example, in a hotel room developed by Marriott in collaboration with Samsung and Legrand SA, there is a growing demand for showers that remember the customer's favorite water temperature, wall pictures that can be changed to family photos, and a display that can show video on voice request. Since last year, the introduction of new types of rooms in "Marriott" hotels has begun. They were the first to be offered by the "W-Hotels" chain. In this regard, "Hilton" recently

presented "smart numbers". In "Smart Numbers" you can control TV, lighting, air temperature and images in digital frames using a mobile application.

The construction of hotels based on innovative technologies in Uzbekistan will be carried out intensively until 2025, taking into account the international experience. According to the plan, 212 new hotels with a total number of 4664 rooms were to be built. Modern hotels were built in Tashkent (41), Samarkand (30) and Bukhara (29), which is in high demand and has the highest number of tourists. Until 2021, their number will be gradually increased, and by this time, 1,508 new hotels with a total number of 30,212 rooms will be founded.

Thus, in 2021, the number of hotels in Uzbekistan will reach 2394. The number of rooms in them is 50044. By January 1, 2022, 50 thousand additional hotel places will be created. Investors who built a three-star hotel with no less than 50 beds will receive 40 million for each room in the hotel. 65 million soums and 65 mln. a subsidy of soum is given.

In addition, the first 50 three-star hotels will be compensated USD 200 per room per year, and the 30 four-star hotels will be compensated USD 400 per room per year. For example, for a hotel with 100 rooms, this means 40 thousand US dollars per year. Such a privilege has not yet been offered anywhere. Such incentives provide the hotel industry with additional opportunities to engage in innovation.

Conclusions and suggestions. Summing up from the above, it is appropriate to define the following direction, which should be given special attention, first of all, considering the continuation of the work started in recent years in the use of digital innovative technologies in the formation of tourism infrastructure, they are:

-acceleration of the use of innovative technologies in affordable accommodation facilities such as modern and brand hotels and hostels, family guest houses, as well as implementation of mechanisms for providing apartments under the AirB&B system;

-creating a system for tourists on cultural heritage subjects through practical information-references, implementing smart-tourism technologies, increasing the efficiency of cultural heritage subjects, museums, theaters, art galleries by installing turnstiles and video surveillance systems;

- creating a republican group to study the issues of effective application of digital innovative technologies in tourism and during the year the experts of local ministries and agencies to thoroughly study the situation together with the experts and representatives of the tourism sector and to find solutions to the problems that prevent the use of innovations in tourism. should be developed.

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